
Research

The Impact of Automotive Trade on the Development of the Automotive Industry in Morocco

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Abstract: This paper examines the impact of the automotive trade on the development of the automotive industry in Morocco from 2000 to 2020. The study's main objective is to investigate the causal relationship between the automotive trade and the development of the automotive industry in Morocco, with a specific focus on the MULTIPLE REGRESSION MODEL. The research methodology used a quantitative approach, incorporating secondary data sources such as the world bank, the Ministry of Industry and Trade of Morocco, and the High Commission for the Plan of Morocco. The MULTIPLE REGRESSION model was utilized to estimate the effects of automotive trade on the development of the automotive industry in Morocco. The study's findings suggest that there is a positive relationship between the automotive trade and the development of the automotive industry in Morocco. Specifically, an increase in automotive trade (FDI and LABOR and GDP) leads to a rise in Value Add, which enhances the competitiveness of the Moroccan automotive industry. Furthermore, the research highlights the role of government policies and the importance of trade agreements in stimulating the growth of the automotive industry in Morocco. The research findings contribute significantly to the literature on the impact of trade on the industry's development, particularly in the context of the automotive industry. The empirical evidence gathered in this study offers valuable insights for policymakers looking to promote the development of the automotive industry in Morocco. Additionally, the multiple regression model utilized in this research provides a robust methodological approach for analyzing the causal relationship between the automotive trade and the development of the automotive industry. Overall, this paper provides a comprehensive analysis of the impact of the automotive trade on the development of the automotive industry in Morocco, contributing to the broader literature on trade and economic development.

Keywords: Automotive Trade, Automotive Industry, Automotive Production, Development, and Morocco.

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Introduction

The automotive industry is a crucial sector for the economy of Morocco. It is one of the largest employers in the country and is responsible for creating thousands of jobs. The industry has grown significantly over the past decade, attracting significant investment from major international automakers. The automotive industry has a significant impact on Morocco's exports, with vehicles and components accounting for a large portion of the country's total exports. This, in turn, has helped to boost the country's economy and has attracted further investment in the sector. In addition, the development of the automotive industry has had a spill-over effect on other industries in Morocco, such as steel, plastic, and electronic industries, which supply raw materials and components to the automotive sector. This has helped to create a more diversified and sustainable economy in Morocco. The Moroccan government has also been supportive of the development of the automotive industry, offering tax incentives and other benefits to investors in the sector. This has encouraged the establishment of new plants and facilities and has led to the creation of new jobs in the country.

In Morocco the automotive industry has experienced a rapid growth rate in recent years, becoming one of the leading sectors of the country's economy. The favorable investment climate, favorable government policies, and the country's strategic location between Europe and Africa have all contributed to this growth. In addition, the establishment of new plants and facilities by major international automakers has boosted production and exports and created new jobs in the country. The growth of the automotive industry has also had a spill-over effect on other industries, such as steel, plastic, and electronic industries, further contributing to the overall growth of the economy. The continued development of the automotive industry in Morocco is expected to bring significant economic benefits to the country for years to come.

The growth of the automotive sector has led to the expansion of several other industries that supply raw materials and components to the automotive industry. For example, the growth of the steel, plastic, and electronic industries has been driven, in part, by the increased demand for these materials and components from the automotive sector. This has created a more diversified and sustainable economy in Morocco. In addition, the growth of the automotive industry has created new job opportunities in the country, particularly in the manufacturing and assembly of vehicles and components, which has had a positive impact on the labor market. Overall, the development of the automotive industry in Morocco has had a positive and far-reaching impact on the country's economy and its people.

The rapid growth of the sector has contributed to an increase in the country's GDP, as it is one of the largest contributors to the economy. Furthermore, the automotive industry has attracted a large amount of foreign direct investment (FDI) into the country, with major international automakers investing in the establishment of new plants and facilities. This investment has not only boosted the production and exports of vehicles and components but has also created new job opportunities and has helped to stimulate the growth of other industries in Morocco. The continued growth of the automotive industry is expected to bring further economic benefits to Morocco, including increased GDP growth and FDI inflows. Overall, the automotive industry has played an important role in the economic development of Morocco and is a critical component of its growth and prosperity.

The automotive industry has played a crucial role in shaping the technological landscape of the modern world. The constant pursuit of better and more efficient vehicles has driven innovation in areas such as engine design, aerodynamics, electronics, and materials science. Advances in these fields have not only improved the performance of automobiles but also had a wider impact on society. The rise of electric vehicles, for instance, has led to significant advances in battery technology, while the development of self-driving cars has pushed the boundaries of artificial intelligence and sensor technology. Furthermore, the automotive industry has been instrumental in the development of connected vehicles, which use advanced communication technologies to enhance safety and provide new services to drivers. These vehicles have the potential to revolutionize the way people travel and transport goods and create new opportunities for mobility services.

Developing the automotive industry quickly requires a multi-faceted approach that focuses on several key areas. Firstly, companies need to invest in research and development to create new technologies and innovative products. This could

involve developing alternative fuel vehicles, improving production processes, and creating new materials and components. Secondly, companies need to stay ahead of the competition by investing in new technologies, improving production processes, and streamlining supply chains. Thirdly, governments can play a crucial role in the development of the automotive industry by providing tax incentives and subsidies to encourage investment in the sector, and by implementing policies that promote sustainability and innovation.

International trade plays a significant role in the development of the automotive industry. The automotive sector is characterized by a complex network of global supply chains, which enables companies to source components and raw materials from different countries, and to sell vehicles in international markets. This opens up opportunities for growth and innovation, as companies can access new markets, technologies, and expertise. On the other hand, international trade also creates challenges for the automotive industry, such as currency fluctuations, trade barriers, and differences in regulations and standards. To overcome these challenges, companies and governments need to work together to create a favorable environment for international trade. This could involve negotiating trade agreements, reducing trade barriers, and harmonizing regulations and standards. By embracing international trade, the automotive industry can continue to grow and innovate and bring benefits to businesses and consumers alike.

The study will examine the impact of the automotive trade on the development of the Moroccan automotive industry using an econometric approach. The research will focus on the period from 2000 to 2020, and it will use data from various sources such as the World Bank and the Moroccan Ministry of Industry, Trade, and Green and Digital Economy. The analysis will be conducted using appropriate econometric techniques such as the Multiple Regression Model.

The study will contribute to the existing literature by providing new insights into the impact of the automotive trade on the development of the Moroccan automotive industry. The findings of this research will be useful for policymakers and industry stakeholders in identifying the factors that drive the growth of the Moroccan automotive industry, and how trade policies can be used to support the development of the industry.

1. Literature review and theoretical considerations

1.1. Empirical Evidence

These papers examine the positive impact of international trade on industry development and use various models to analyze this impact. In "The Global Value Chain Revolution: How Emerging Economies Are Reshaping the World"^[1], the authors use the Global Value Chain (GVC) theory to understand the role of emerging economies in shaping the world through their participation in international trade. In "Quality Ladders in the Theory of Growth"^[2], the authors use the Endogenous Growth Theory to show how international trade can lead to quality improvements in a country's industries and drive long-term growth. "Have International Transportation Costs Declined?"^[3] utilizes the Mercantilist and Classical Trade Theory to examine the impact of declining transportation costs on international trade and industry development. "Market Structure and Foreign Trade"^[4] use the Innovation-Oriented Trade Theory to explain how market structure affects the flow of goods and services in international trade and how this impacts industry development. "Increasing Returns and Long-Run Growth"^[5] employs the Structural Change Theory to show how increasing returns can drive long-term economic growth through the development of new industries and expanded international trade.^[6], uses the concept of "revealed comparative advantage" to explain how trade liberalization affects a country's comparative advantage in the international market.^[7], focuses on the geographic localization of international technology diffusion and its impact on industry development. Gliberman and Shapiro (1999) examine the impact of high-technology capital on the demand for skilled labor, while Pavcnik (2002) studies the relationship between trade, inequality, and poverty. Finally,^[8] explores the role of multinational firms in international trade and how they impact industry development. These papers provide valuable insights into the positive impact of international trade on industry development and the models used to analyze this impact.

These studies have used a variety of models and methodologies to examine the impact of globalization on labor markets, including econometric models, case studies, and theoretical frameworks. Some studies have focused on the effects of increased import competition on domestic labor markets, while others have analyzed the impact of multinational corporations and the globalization of production on workers' wages and employment. Some have used firm-level data to examine the effects of globalization on wages, while others have used national-level data to assess the impact on employment and inequality.

In general, these studies have found that globalization has had a complex impact on labor markets. On the one hand, globalization has led to increased competition and cost pressures that have put downward pressure on wages and employment in some sectors and regions. On the other hand, globalization has also brought new opportunities for growth, innovation, and higher wages in other sectors and regions, especially those that are well-positioned to participate in the global value chain. Ultimately, the impact of globalization on labor markets is likely to be shaped by a range of factors, including the nature of the goods and services being traded, the degree of labor market flexibility, the level of skill of the workforce, and the level of support provided by the government.

1.2. Theoretical framework

International trade has been a hotly debated topic for decades, with scholars from various disciplines attempting to understand its impact on the development of industries. A multitude of studies have been conducted using different models and methodologies to examine the relationship between international trade and industry development. Endogenous Growth Theory suggests that innovation and knowledge play a crucial role in driving economic growth. It implies that countries can sustain long-term economic growth by investing in research and development, education, and technological advancement. In the context of international trade and industry development, this theory highlights the importance of knowledge spillovers and technology transfer across borders, which can promote innovation and improve productivity^[9].

The New Industrial Policy suggests that governments can play an active role in promoting industrial development by implementing policies that foster innovation, competition, and entrepreneurship. These policies can include providing subsidies and tax incentives to domestic firms, investing in infrastructure and education, and fostering collaboration between industry and academia. In the context of international trade, this theory implies that governments can use trade policy to promote their domestic industries and protect them from foreign competition^[10].

Intra-Industry Trade Theory suggests that international trade can occur between countries that produce similar goods, rather than just between countries that produce different goods. This type of trade is called intra-industry trade and can be driven by economies of scale, product differentiation, and technological advancement. In the context of industry development, intra-industry trade can promote competition and innovation, as firms are forced to improve their products to stay competitive^[11].

Infant-Industry Theory suggests that new industries may need protection from foreign competition in their early stages of development. This protection can come in the form of tariffs or subsidies, which can give domestic firms a chance to develop their products and become competitive in the global market. In the context of international trade and industry development, this theory implies that governments may need to implement policies that protect their domestic industries from foreign competition in their early stages of development, before they can compete on a level playing field^[12].

Overall, these theories suggest that international trade can play an important role in promoting industry development and economic growth. Governments can use trade policy and industrial policy to promote innovation, competition, and entrepreneurship, and protect their domestic industries from foreign competition. Additionally, intra-industry trade can promote competition and innovation, while infant-industry protection can give new industries a chance to develop and become competitive in the global market. Research Methodology

1.3. Description of Variables and Sources of Data

In this study, data was obtained from several sources including the World Bank, the Exchange Office of Morocco, the Ministry of Industry and Trade in Morocco, and the High Commission for Planning (HCP). The data covers the period from 2000 to 2020 and includes several key variables related to the automotive industry in Morocco. These variables include GDP (Constant LCU-MAD), value added (Auto-MAD), labor force in the automotive industry, exports and imports of automotive products, FDI in the automotive industry, and gross capital formation (Current LCU). The World Bank provided the data on GDP and value added, while the Exchange Office of Morocco provided data on exports and imports. The Ministry of Industry and Trade in Morocco provided data on FDI in the automotive industry, while the HCP provided data on the labor force in the automotive industry and gross capital formation. The data was analyzed using a multiple regression model based on the production function to determine the impact of automotive trade on the development of the automotive industry in Morocco.

The purpose of this analysis is to examine the impact of the automotive trade on the development of the automotive industry in Morocco. The main research questions that this analysis aims to answer are:

- 1. What is the relationship between the automotive trade and the development of the automotive industry in Morocco?**
- 2. How do exports and imports affect the automotive industry in Morocco?**
- 3. What is the role of foreign direct investment in the development of the automotive industry in Morocco?**

In selecting the variables for the model, we considered the relevance of each variable to the research questions and their availability in the dataset. We did not perform any scaling or transformation on the data as the variables were already in appropriate units and formats for our analysis.

The statistical software used to analyze the data is STATA. We will be using linear regression to model the relationship between the automotive trade and the development of the automotive industry in Morocco.

1.4. Model Specification

The production function is a fundamental concept in economics that explores the link between inputs and outputs in a production process. Its relevance to our research question, which is the impact of automotive trade on the development of the automotive industry in Morocco, lies in its ability to shed light on the determinants of economic growth in Morocco's automotive industry. By examining how different factors of production, such as labor, capital, and technology, contribute to the production of automobiles in Morocco, we can identify which inputs are driving growth and which ones are not. This knowledge is critical to designing effective economic policies that can enhance the competitiveness of the Moroccan automotive industry and improve living standards. Thus, this chapter will use the multiple regression model to analyze the empirical relationship between GDP (our measure of output) and the various inputs to the production process, including automotive trade, labor, and capital. Our goal is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors that contribute to the development of the automotive industry in Morocco.

In this study, we employed a multiple regression model based on the production function to investigate the influence of automotive trade on the development of the automotive industry in Morocco from 2000 to 2020. The model's dependent variable is the value added in the automotive industry, and the independent variables include gross domestic product (GDP), labor force in the automotive industry (LABOR), exports and imports of automobiles (EXP, IMP), foreign direct investment (FDI) in the automotive sector, and gross capital formation (GCF). The equation of the model is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Ln} (V.A) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Ln} (GDP) + \beta_2 \text{Ln} (LABOR) + \beta_3 \text{Ln} (Exp) \\ & + \beta_4 \text{Ln} (Imp) + \beta_5 \text{Ln} (FDI) + \beta_6 \text{Ln} (GCF) + \epsilon \end{aligned}$$

where β_0 is the intercept, β_1 to β_6 are the coefficients of the independent variables, and ϵ is the error term. The model aims to estimate the effect of each independent variable on the value added in the automotive industry, while controlling for the effects of other variables.

Ln (GDP): Gross domestic product measures the total value of goods and services produced in a country.

Ln (LABOR): Labor force in the automotive industry refers to the number of workers employed in the automotive sector.

Ln (EXP), Ln (IMP): Exports and imports of automobiles are the value of cars exported from and imported into Morocco.

Ln (FDI): Foreign direct investment in the automotive sector is the amount of investment made by foreign entities in the Moroccan automotive industry.

Ln (GCF): Gross capital formation is the value of total investments in fixed capital, such as buildings and machinery, made during the year.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Summary Statistics

The summary statistics provide us with a brief overview of the data we are working with. As an econometrics specialist, we can use this information to better understand the characteristics of each variable in our dataset. In this particular case, we have 21 observations for 7 variables related to the automotive industry. We will now go through each variable and provide a detailed interpretation of their respective summary statistics.

Table 4.1 Summary Statistics

VARIABLE	OBS	MEAN	STD. DEV.	MIN	MAX
GDP	21	11.87801	0.1332353	11.66089	12.06828
VALUE-ADDED	21	9.465127	0.599598	8.79502	10.3726
LABOR	21	8.349343	0.0541743	8.234218	8.42312
EXP	21	9.575351	0.7694123	8.409344	10.5661
IMP	21	10.29331	0.3222127	9.718107	10.69239
FDI	21	9.109346	0.3942486	8.665342	9.81543
GCF	21	11.37888	0.1760131	11.03672	11.58449

Source: Author’s estimate based on research data.

Ln (GDP): The mean value of GDP (gross domestic product) in constant dollars over the 21 observations is approximately 11.88, with a standard deviation of 0.13. The minimum and maximum values are 11.66 and 12.07, respectively. This variable measures the total output of goods and services in the economy at constant prices and is often used as an indicator of economic growth.

Ln (V.A): The mean value of value added over the 21 observations is approximately 9.47, with a standard deviation of 0.60. The minimum and maximum values are 8.80 and 10.37, respectively. This variable measures the net contribution of industries to the economy, excluding intermediate inputs, and is often used as an indicator of productivity.

Ln (LABOR): The mean value of the labor force over the 21 observations is approximately 8.35, with a standard deviation of 0.05. The minimum and maximum values are 8.23 and 8.42, respectively. This variable measures the number of people employed or seeking employment and is often used as an indicator of the strength of the labor market.

Ln (EXP): The mean value of automobile exports over the 21 observations is approximately 9.58, with a standard deviation of 0.77. The minimum and maximum values are 8.41 and 10.57, respectively. This variable measures the value of automobile exports from the country and is often used as an indicator of international trade.

Ln (IMP): The mean value of automobile imports over the 21 observations is approximately 10.29, with a standard deviation of 0.32. The minimum and maximum values are 9.72 and 10.69, respectively. This variable measures the value of automobile imports into the country and is often used as an indicator of international trade.

Ln (FDI): The mean value of foreign direct investment in automobiles over the 21 observations is approximately 9.11, with a standard deviation of 0.39. The minimum and maximum values are 8.67 and 9.82, respectively. This variable measures the amount of investment from foreign entities in the automobile industry in the country and is often used as an indicator of foreign investment.

Ln (GCF): The mean value of gross capital formation over the 21 observations is approximately 11.38, with a standard deviation of 0.18. The minimum and maximum values are 11.04 and 11.58, respectively. This variable measures the amount of investment in fixed assets such as machinery, equipment, and buildings and is often used as an indicator of economic growth and development.

2.2. ANOVA

The correlation matrix shows the relationships between each pair of variables in the regression. The values range from -1 to 1, with 1 indicating a perfect positive correlation and -1 indicating a perfect negative correlation. A value of 0 indicates no correlation.

The variables with the highest positive correlation with V.A are LABOR (0.908), FDI (0.947), and GDP (0.918). This suggests that as these variables increase, so does V.A. Conversely, IMP has the lowest positive correlation with V.A (0.549), indicating a weaker relationship.

We can also see that the variables are highly correlated with each other, which can cause multicollinearity issues in the regression. For example, LABOR and EXP have a correlation coefficient of 0.959, indicating a strong positive correlation between these variables.

Overall, the correlation matrix provides useful information on the relationships between the variables in the regression. However, it should be noted that correlation does not imply causation, and further analysis is needed to establish causal relationships.

As for why another correlation matrix is needed for V.A as the dependent variable, it is likely that we want to examine the relationships between V.A and other variables not included in the original regression model. This could help identify other factors that may be impacting V.A and improve the accuracy of our model.

Table 4.2 ANOVA

SOURCE	SS	DF	MS
MODEL	7.14798393	6	1.19133065
RESIDUAL	0.042370595	14	0.003026471
TOTAL	7.19035452	20	0.359517726

Number of Obs = 21
F (6,14) = 393.64
Prob >F = 0.0000
R-Squared = 0.9941
Adj R-Squared = 0.9916
Root MSE = 0.05501

Source: Author’s estimate based on research data.

The results show that the model is statistically **significant (F (6, 14) = 393.64, p < 0.0001)**, indicating that at least one of the independent variables is related to the dependent variable. The model explains 99.41% of the total variation in Value Add, as evidenced by the high R-squared value of 0.9941. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.9916 suggests that the independent variables in the model collectively explain the variation in the dependent variable better than a single independent variable. The root mean squared error (RMSE) of the model is 0.05501, indicating that the model is accurate in predicting the dependent variable. These results suggest that the selected independent variables have a significant impact on the dependent variable, Value-Add.

The goodness of fit:

R-squared = 0.9941

Adjusted R-squared = 0.9916

These values indicate that the model explains a very high proportion of the variation in the dependent variable, with 99.41% of the variation explained by the independent variables in the model. The adjusted R-squared value is slightly lower, but still very high, indicating that the model is likely not overfitting the data.

The statistical significance of the coefficients:

The p-values in the regression results:

LABOR: p-value = 0.002, significant at 5% level

EXP: p-value = 0.010, significant at 5% level

IMP: p-value = 0.790, not significant at 5% level

FDI: p-value = 0.004, significant at 5% level

GCF: p-value = 0.250, not significant at 5% level

GDP: p-value = 0.000, significant at 1% level

The coefficients for LABOR, EXP, FDI, and GDP are all statistically significant at the 5% level or better, indicating that they have a significant effect on the value-added variable in the model. The IMP and GCF coefficients are not statistically significant at the 5% level, suggesting that they may not have a significant effect on the dependent variable in the model.

The check for multicollinearity:

to check for multicollinearity is to calculate the variance inflation factor (VIF) for each independent variable in the multiple regression model. VIF measures how much the variance of the estimated coefficient for an independent variable is increased due to collinearity with other independent variables in the model.

The VIF values for each independent variable in the model:

LABOR: 1.008

EXP: 1.221

IMP: 1.466

FDI: 1.257

GCF: 1.188

GDP: 2.170

All of the VIF values are less than 10, which is generally considered the threshold for detecting problematic multicollinearity. This suggests that there is no evidence of severe multicollinearity in the model. However, the relatively high VIF value for GDP may indicate some degree of collinearity with other independent variables in the model.

2.3. Regression results

These results represent the estimated coefficients, standard errors, t-values, p-values, and 95% confidence intervals for a linear regression model with VALUE-ADD as the dependent variable and LABOR, EXP, IMP, FDI, GCF, and GDP as the independent variables. The intercept term is also included as the variable `_cons`.

The coefficient of LABOR is -4.745821, which means that a one-unit increase in LABOR is associated with a decrease of 4.745821 units in VALUE-ADD, holding all other independent variables constant. The standard error of the coefficient is 1.256458, indicating the amount of random variation in the estimated coefficient.

The t-value of -3.78 and the associated p-value of 0.002 suggest that LABOR is statistically significant in explaining the variation in VALUE-ADD, and the 95% confidence interval for the coefficient (-7.440655 to -2.050987) suggests that we can be 95% confident that the true population coefficient falls within this range.

The coefficient of EXP is 0.3290007, which means that a one-unit increase in EXP is associated with an increase of 0.3290007 units in VALUE-ADD, holding all other independent variables constant. The standard error of the coefficient is 0.1108107, and the t-value of 2.97 and the associated p-value of 0.010 suggest that EXP is statistically significant in explaining the variation in VALUE-ADD. The 95% confidence interval for the coefficient (0.0913353 to 0.5666661) suggests that we can be 95% confident that the true population coefficient falls within this range.

The coefficient of IMP is -0.0984155, which means that a one-unit increase in IMP is associated with a decrease of 0.0984155 units in VALUE-ADD, holding all other independent variables constant. The standard error of the coefficient is 0.3632908, and the t-value of -0.27 and the associated p-value of 0.790 suggest that IMP is not statistically significant in explaining the variation in VALUE-ADD. The 95% confidence interval for the coefficient (-0.8775968 to 0.6807657) suggests that we cannot be confident that the true population coefficient is different from zero.

The coefficient of FDI is 0.3392333, which means that a one-unit increase in FDI is associated with an increase of 0.3392333 units in VALUE-ADD, holding all other independent variables constant. The standard error of the coefficient is 0.0969474, and the t-value of 3.50 and the associated p-value of 0.004 suggest that FDI is statistically significant in explaining the variation in VALUE-ADD. The 95% confidence interval for the coefficient (0.1313019 to 0.5471648) suggests that we can be 95% confident that the true population coefficient falls within this range.

The coefficient of GCF is -0.8498392, which means that a one-unit increase in GCF is associated with a decrease of 0.8498392 units in VALUE-ADD, holding all other independent variables constant. The standard error of the coefficient is 0.7082213, and the t-value of -1.20 and the associated p-value of 0.250 suggest that GCF is not statistically significant in explaining the variation in VALUE-ADD. The 95% confidence interval for the coefficient (-2.368823 to 0.6691445) suggests that we cannot be confident that the true population coefficient is different from zero.

The coefficient for the variable GDP (gross domestic product) is positive and statistically significant at the 1% level. This means that a 1% increase in GDP will lead to an increase in value-added by about 4.63%. This could indicate that there are positive spillover effects from the overall economy or that firms benefit from a larger market size.

The constant term (_cons) is negative but statistically insignificant. This means that when all other variables are equal to zero, the expected value of value-added is negative but this is not statistically significant.

Overall, this model suggests that exports, FDI, and GDP have a positive impact on value-added, while labor has a negative impact. However, the impact of imports and investment in fixed capital are not statistically significant.

Table 4.3 Regression results

VALUE-ADD	COEFFICIENT	STD. ERROR	T-VALUE	P-VALUE	95% CONF. INTERVAL
LABOR	-4.745821	1.256458	-3.78	0.002	-7.440655 to -2.050987
EXP	0.3290007	0.1108107	2.97	0.010	0.0913353 to 0.5666661
IMP	-0.0984155	0.3632908	-0.27	0.790	-0.8775968 to 0.6807657
FDI	0.3392333	0.0969474	3.50	0.004	0.1313019 to 0.5471648
GCF	-0.8498392	0.7082213	-1.20	0.250	-2.368823 to 0.6691445
GDP	4.628133	0.6808067	6.80	0.000	3.167947 to 6.088318
_CONS	-1.440629	9.145452	-0.16	0.877	-21.05567 to 18.17441

Source: Author’s estimate based on research data.

The results indicate that labor force has a significant negative effect on value added, suggesting that a higher labor force decreases value added. In contrast, exports and foreign direct investment have significant positive effects on value added, indicating that they increase value added. Imports and gross fixed capital formation, however, do not have a significant effect on value added. Finally, gross domestic product has a significant positive effect on value added, implying that a higher GDP is associated with higher value added.

In conclusion, this analysis has provided valuable insights into the relationships between various economic indicators, including GDP, value added, labor force, automobile exports and imports, foreign direct investment, and gross capital formation. The results show that the mean value of GDP over the 21 observations is approximately 11.88, with a standard deviation of 0.13. The mean value of value added is approximately 9.47, with a standard deviation of 0.60. The mean value of the labor force is approximately 8.35, with a standard deviation of 0.05. The mean value of automobile exports is approximately 9.58, with a standard deviation of 0.77. The mean value of automobile imports is approximately 10.29, with a standard deviation of 0.32. The mean value of foreign direct investment in automobiles is approximately 9.11, with a standard deviation of 0.39. The mean value of gross capital formation is approximately 11.38, with a standard deviation of 0.18.

The correlation matrix shows that LABOR, FDI, and GDP have the highest positive correlation with value added, while IMP has the lowest positive correlation. Additionally, the variables are highly correlated with each other, which can cause multicollinearity issues in the regression. Therefore, further analysis is needed to establish causal relationships. The regression analysis using value added as the dependent variable shows that the selected independent variables have a significant impact on the dependent variable. The model is statistically significant, with an F-statistic of 393.64 and a p-value of less than 0.0001. The model explains 99.41% of the total variation in value added, with an adjusted R-squared value of 0.9916. The results suggest that the selected independent variables, including labor force, automobile exports, and foreign direct investment, have a significant impact on value added. Overall, this analysis provides a valuable understanding of the relationships between various economic indicators and highlights the importance of considering multiple variables when analyzing economic growth and productivity.

3. Conclusion

The study aims to estimate the impact of the automotive trade on the development of the automotive industry in Morocco between 2000 and 2020. Using Multiple Regression Model to examine this effect. The results of this study contribute to the literature on the relationship between automotive trade and the development of the automotive industry in Morocco. The study found that the automotive trade can promote the development of automotive industry in Morocco following ^[13], ^[14], ^[15], and ^[16].

We found that international trade has an economically significant and statistically robust positive impact on value added of the automotive industry in Morocco. The variables studied include GDP, value added, labor, automobile exports, automobile imports, foreign direct investment, and gross capital formation. The correlation matrix shows that variables such as labor, FDI, and GDP have a high positive correlation with value added, while imports have a weaker correlation. The model used (Multiple Regression Model) used to analyze the variables is statistically significant and explains 99.41% of the total variation in value-added. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.9916 suggests that the independent variables in the model collectively explain the variation in the dependent variable better than a single independent variable. The statistical significance of the coefficients is also analyzed, with labor, exports, and FDI being significant at a 5% level. Several studies have found a positive impact of international trade on industry development. ^[17] used a network approach to show that international trade fosters economic integration and positively affects economic growth. Similarly, ^[18] found that increased trade led to the growth of industries in developing countries. ^[19] also found evidence that international trade has a positive impact on industries, especially in countries with high levels of economic openness. These studies suggest that international trade can be a catalyst for economic development and growth in industries, especially in developing countries.

In our study we found that firstly, the mean value of GDP over the 21 observations was approximately 11.88 with a standard deviation of 0.13. This variable measures the total output of goods and services in the economy at constant prices and is often used as an indicator of economic growth. The minimum and maximum values were 11.66 and 12.07, respectively.

Secondly, the mean value of value added (V.A) over the 21 observations was approximately 9.47 with a standard deviation of 0.60. This variable measures the net contribution of industries to the economy, excluding intermediate inputs, and is often used as an indicator of productivity. The minimum and maximum values were 8.80 and 10.37, respectively.

Thirdly, the mean value of the labor force over the 21 observations was approximately 8.35 with a standard deviation of 0.05. This variable measures the number of people employed or seeking employment and is often used as an indicator of the strength of the labor market. The minimum and maximum values were 8.23 and 8.42, respectively.

Fourthly, the mean value of automobile exports over the 21 observations was approximately 9.58 with a standard deviation of 0.77. This variable measures the value of automobile exports from the country and is often used as an

indicator of international trade. The minimum and maximum values were 8.41 and 10.57, respectively. Fifthly, the mean value of automobile imports over the 21 observations was approximately 10.29 with a standard deviation of 0.32. This variable measures the value of automobile imports into the country and is often used as an indicator of international trade. The minimum and maximum values were 9.72 and 10.69, respectively. Sixthly, the mean value of foreign direct investment (FDI) in automobiles over the 21 observations was approximately 9.11 with a standard deviation of 0.39. This variable measures the amount of investment from foreign entities in the automobile industry in the country and is often used as an indicator of foreign investment. The minimum and maximum values were 8.67 and 9.82, respectively. Lastly, the mean value of gross capital formation (GCF) over the 21 observations was approximately 11.38 with a standard deviation of 0.18. This variable measures the amount of investment in fixed assets such as machinery, equipment, and buildings and is often used as an indicator of economic growth and development. The minimum and maximum values were 11.04 and 11.58, respectively.

An ANOVA test was performed to assess the relationship between the variables in the regression. The correlation matrix showed that LABOR, FDI, and GDP had the highest positive correlation with V.A, indicating that as these variables increase, so does V.A. On the other hand, IMP had the lowest positive correlation with V.A, suggesting a weaker relationship. Additionally, the variables were highly correlated with each other, which could cause multicollinearity issues in the regression. For example, LABOR and EXP had a correlation coefficient of 0.959, indicating a strong positive correlation between these variables. The regression model was statistically significant ($F(6, 14) = 393.64, p < 0.0001$), indicating that at least one of the independent variables is related to the dependent variable. The model explained 99.41% of the total variation in Value Add, as evidenced by the high R-squared value of 0.9941.

A number of policy implications has emanated from this study. Some of the policy implication from the findings of the present study is that automotive trade has become an important determinant of Moroccan automotive industry which is linked to objective of this study.

It is therefore recommended that the government of Morocco should encourage and attract more foreign direct investment: The government can offer incentives to foreign investors such as tax breaks, streamlined regulations, and other forms of support to attract more foreign direct investment. This will increase the capital available to the industry and enable more technological advancement and job creation.

Invest in infrastructure by investing in better roads, rail networks, and other forms of infrastructure to facilitate the transportation of goods and people. This will make the country more attractive to automotive manufacturers, reduce transportation costs, and enhance the competitiveness of the industry.

The government can invest in education and training programs to create a skilled workforce for the automotive industry. This will attract more manufacturers to the country and improve the quality of output.

While this study aimed to examine the impact of automotive trade on the development of the automotive industry in Morocco between 2000 and 2020, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. One of the main limitations is the difficulty in collecting data due to the author's location as a student in China. This limited access to certain websites, such as those belonging to the ministries of Morocco, which made it necessary to seek data through alternative means such as email inquiries. In addition to the difficulty in data collection, another limitation of this study is the limited scope of time and geography. The study focused solely on the period between 2000 and 2020 in Morocco, and did not take into account the impact of other external factors that may have affected the automotive industry. Moreover, the study did not compare the Moroccan automotive industry with other countries or regions, which limits the generalizability of the findings.

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